

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ISSUES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In the fast growing world the physical education emphasizes to have a healthy life style of a child. Everyone likes to take part in physical activity but it is not continued properly as the prime importance is given to academics. Development around the world has made Physical Education & Sports an important part of our life. The difficulties faced by the physical educationist and necessity to overcome the problems are presented in the study. Moreover the role of technology has also made a revolution in this era. The Physical Education teachers ought to be ready to adopt and keep posted to utilise the modern equipments, methods and systems. As an outcome a child shall learn to have a healthy lifestyle and the physical education shall grow along with other areas and shall produce fruitful results to the individual and to the society. The neglected discipline has started receiving importance these days in all the strata's of human beings. Hence due importance to physical education teaching & sports is being given due attention. Sports person are considered to be the best ambassadors of the nation & the same can be true for a teacher in physical education in Schools & Colleges. The overall scenario doesn't seem to be encouraging as there is reduced demand for physical education instead of increased risk of life for a common individual. The paper discusses the present scenario of physical education & sports technology and its contemporary issues in India.

Keywords: Physical Education, Sports Technology, Contemporary Issues, India.

INTRODUCTION:

The importance of physical education has never been emphasised more than it is today. It is widely recognised that physical education and sports are relevant and important in developing an active and healthy lifestyle and the solution to rising obesity rate worldwide. Although in most countries, physical education is part of the school curriculum. The lessons are not given, leading to a reduced experience of physical activity for children and youth. The practice of a physically active lifestyle in combination with healthy nutrition needs to be started in early childhood. Quality Physical Education is the most effective and inclusive means of providing all children, whatever their ability/disability, sex, age, cultural, race/ethnicity, religious or social background, with the skills, attitudes, values, knowledge and understanding for lifelong participation in physical activity and sport and is the only school subject whose primary focus is on the body, physical activity, physical development and health.

The Physical education (PE) is an integral part of school curriculum. It's not a detach area from others. As an outcome of research, schemes, advanced technology, critical issues, awareness of health, it has become essential to develop the quality of PE programmes. Today it has been renowned that PE is relevant and necessary to develop a healthy lifestyle. Some misconceptions are there in the mind among school authorities, parents and students that PE activities requires lot of time allotment, may affect academics and chance of injuries are more. In case of severe injury and due to the insufficient availability of proper facility, trained people, doctors and physiotherapists the rehabilitation process it may keep them away from the academics and sports for many days. There are many potential children at the international standard but the traditional inclination has kept them away from involving. PE and

sport is vital for the overall development of the child. It helps to achieve mind body unity, learn to be calm during victory and accept the defeat graciously in a sportive behaviour. PE is a scientific as well as technical subject. Yet, the PE and sports programmes are neglected and funds are allotted for the private associations. Thus it makes a variation from competitive sports. Competitive sports are good for economy, but at the same time it is more necessary to have good health and the entire development of the child shall be the primary focus. In this paper the current issues in PE and the problem faced by the physical educationists in India have been discussed.

PHYSICAL EDUCATION & SPORTS: INDIAN SCENARIO

Physical Education & Sports forms an important part of educational system even when it never received the importance it deserves. Even though it is included as part of the curriculum from the early stages of education, it has never been taken seriously by the educational administrators, the academicians and the students. Physical Education is the only profession where you talk as well as play / perform. The concept of Physical Education in the mind of general public is big round, play & play and no work. Abraham Lincoln quoted in one of his address, "Sportsman is the best Ambassador of the Nation." Hence, the Physical Education Director/Teacher can also be the best Ambassador of our Institution / University. The problem of defining Physical Education is not only that the term is broad based and complex, including so many kinds of phenomena, but also it means different things to different people. Sports leads to development of total personality of the child and its fulfillment and perfection in body, mind and spirit. Even though this definition differs significantly with regards to emphasis on different aspects, they still have many common elements. Some of them may be noted as: Physical Education is a phase of total Education process. It is sum of total experience and their related responses. Experience grown and responses developed out of participation in big muscular activities. All-round development of individual" – physical, mental, social, moral is the real aim of Physical Education. It is the same as in General Education. In the Indian context, Physical Education is perhaps the only aspect of education which has not been given due attention. That is due, most probably to the fact that we have remained satisfied with what the British have handed over to us, with no sincere efforts on our part to prepare any concrete and far-reaching programme for Physical Education especially suited to our conditions. We have ever-stressed the academic aspects, the physical one being relatively untouched. This has resulted in an increasingly large number of Indians who are neglecting their bodies, to whom Physical Education is similar to physical training, whose physical fitness is not what it should be they are getting 'soft'. One of the main objectives of any Physical Education activity is to maintain and improves the health of the youngsters in our school and colleges. And the School has the responsibility to see that all students achieve and maintain optimum health, not only from a moral point of view, but from the standard point that educational experience will be much more meaningful if optimum health exists. A child learns easier and better when he is in a state of good health. Even ones" values have much to do with health building and destroying activities. Unfortunately, a large number of people suffer from 'value illnesses', i.e. they know what they are supposed to do to keep well, yet they fail to do so. They know that tobacco smoking can cause death from Lung Cancer, even then they do not give up smoking. They understand how alcohol affects the driving ability, yet they drive in a state of drunkenness. They appreciate the role of regular exercise in weight control, yet they do little to alter their sedentary way of living. Education and health & medical authorities have therefore, long recognized the need for a programme of Director Physical Education activities in school curriculum. It is during the formative and rapidly growing period of elementary school-age that foundation of proper habits, attitudes and appreciations toward all physical activities, including play is implied and desirable citizenship traits acquired, so that in adulthood he will be equipped with the knowledge, sound thinking processes, physical stamina and emotional maturity to

live effectively in an ever changing and highly complex society. In that respect, teachers bear a major responsibility in answering that challenge effectively.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

To study Physical Education and sports is not merely to discuss performance, technique or records journalistic-ally but to look at some of the implicit assumptions held by the general population about Physical Education and Sports. Despite the significance of sports, it has been primarily a vehicle of 'escape' more than an avenue of education. A sport has been viewed as a distraction from the trials of everyday life. Despite efforts by member state to promote and develop Physical Education and Sports with international cooperation; its distinctive nature and importance to education remain a constant source of concern. Hence, Physical Education and Sports proved alarming particularly within educational system, which given the social importance and media-coverage of sports. Its impact may be seen in the shift by Physical Education and Sport Public authorities towards high performance and high media friendly sports at a national level.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study on present scenario of physical education & sports technology and its contemporary issues to the India context.
2. To know the current issues in physical education and the problems faced by the physical educationists in India.
3. To analyse the role of physical education and sports in India.
4. To examine the problems faced by women entrepreneurs.
5. To suggest measures for the healthy growth of entrepreneurship being self-employed.

Methodology:

The methodology followed in this study has been mainly a literature study. A wide range of literature was used, including books, relevant journals and published papers. Due to the nature of the subject under discussion, ample use was made of current electronic documents through the internet. The secondary data will be collected from books, journals, census reports, economic surveys, sources of statistical data from official documents, reports and certain periodicals such as economic times, etc. In addition to these, researcher will visit various educational institutions.

Role of Physical Education & Sports:

The Physical Education and Sports preserves the vital clue that exists between Physical Education and Sports. The reciprocal guarantee highlighted the provisions of as such it is necessary to consider Physical Education and Sports as an intrinsic part of education in all schools and colleges in a country, where sports should be compulsory right from elementary school level to till college level. In fact, quality education involves the dispensing the essential requirements of life skills i.e. learning to (i) Self-motivation, creativity and problem solving (ii) Use interactive tools (communication, physical and IT) (iii) To join and live within sociality divers groups. All these Board based life skills are precisely what Physical Education and Sports can develop. Therefore, it goes without saying that Physical Education and Sports must be actively promoted by International organizations, state governments, local authorities. The field of education must coordinate and streamline these efforts to defend the cause of Physical Education and Sports. This will include helping to redress the balance of

Physical Education and sport in Education in its drive to improve the situation of Physical Education and Sports worldwide.

Contemporary Current Issues:

Today, children are more sedentary than ever, due in part to the enormous amount of time spent on phones, computers, and engaging with social media. Because of this, weight-related health issues such as childhood obesity and diabetes are more prevalent in children and have become major health issues. Schools, which once played a huge part in health education are cutting back, or in some cases, eliminating physical education at all grade levels. For some kids, PE may be the only opportunity for physical activity. Unfortunately, many schools are faced with budget cuts, and the first thing to go tends to be PE.

To make up for no physical education program, many schools across the country looked to their physical education trainer for help by means of outsourcing private organizations to provide PE to students. In addition, school physical education teachers are now being encouraged to take on the role of PE teacher, but that has its own problems. Many school physical education teachers are not properly trained to teach physical education to their students. In addition, teachers must teach the required academic lessons, which leaves very little time for them to plan and teach PE. Therefore, the Physical Education teachers ought to be ready to adopt and keep posted to utilise the modern equipments, methods and systems.

Role of technology in Physical Education:

The one and the most reasonably priced mode of technology is simple video recorder. In this the students are in such a position to view their mistakes and rectify, like the glide in the shot put, landing with both the legs, extension of arm, swinging of arms. It is more effective than explaining theoretically or manually. The other mode of technology is the pedometer and heart rate monitors. Pedometer is the most common technology used in the field of PE. It tracks the person where the person is going on. How many steps they have made but it's not absolutely possible to know how far the person is. The average steps they make shall be studied. The heart rate monitors are used to fix the heart rate goals and to study how the exercise affects the body. Today it's a wireless world where everyone are familiar with high speed internet, data connection, tabs, lap top, cell phones, i phones, video games and various apps. These shall be used as one of the tool effectively for the development among children, youths and sportspersons. The downloaded videos helps to know the various movements, world record events, hard fought matches, inspirational talks, research analysis and many required data's shall be shown by using the video projectors. The research trends, healthy habits with the specified and modern explanation and appropriate figures are available to enhance the curriculum offerings in the education system. The growth in the tremendous technological application has emphasized on promoting physical activity, fitness, which is the primary goal in everyone, life. The instructional strategy, different offensive and defensive methods, Habits of various sports persons, Tactics, Health tips all over the world can be known in seconds. Technology has made the students to learn in their way, which is directly a student oriented one. The technology has driven the world in to a challenged and enhanced variety of opportunities for the learners and teachers and researcher. Hence, it is more essential for the health and physical education teachers to update become more responsible in utilising these technologies in an effective manner.

CONCLUSION:

Young people are the assets of any country in the world, with highest under 25 population in the world India stands to gain with more work & output with the Human Resources available, but then preserving the Human Resource & maintaining the longitivity of these young ones is a challenge to India, one of the fastest developing nation of the world. Society on the other hand should provide enough opportunities to its members so that they may engage themselves in activities of their own choice and thus develop or maintain the level of Physical Fitness. Unless there is improvement in the 'General Standard of Health', excellence in sports cannot improve. Physical Education and Sports activities in educational institution should aim at 'Health Related' and 'Performance Related' areas so as to ensure 'enhancement of Performance in competitive sports'. Physical Education thus consists in promoting a systematic all-round development of human body by scientific technique and thereby maintaining extraordinary Physical Fitness to achieve one's cherished goals in life. Hence any organization of Physical Education should start with developing a positive attitude and self-confidence among Physical Educators themselves and make them feel, Physical Education need not exist in the periphery of the schools/ colleges, but should extend itself to the classrooms and become the focus or central point of Educational System.

Physical Education Teachers need to have a lot of extending tasks to keep skills new enough to promote practice. The thematic approaches where movement is incorporated shall be a very flourishing device. Dance, music skills shall be imparted as part of the PE which apparently helps to stimulate and learn at the primary level. The PE teachers ought to be ready to adopt and keep posted to utilise the modern equipments, methods and systems. Sufficient funds shall be allotted to all the activities, sports and games. The educational institutional authorities shall tie up with the various organisations to avail the sponsorship and to promote the physical activities. In various ways and methods the PE teachers should be keeping posted. In this decade the role of technology is vital and shall incorporate to learn effectively and efficiently. As an outcome a child shall learn to have a healthy lifestyle and the physical education shall grow along with other areas and shall produce fruitful results to the individual and to the society.

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